

CHILDREN WITH HEARING IMPAIRMENTS ARE NOT DEPRIVED OF THE OPPORTUNITY TO RECEIVE EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The article discusses the characteristics of children with hearing impairments, emphasizes the importance of studying their specific psychological needs, and highlights the necessity of starting the educational process from an early age, particularly from the preschool period.*

Keywords: *hearing-impaired, innovative technology, sign language, tactile-vibrational sensitivity, inclusiveness, special education strategies.*

ДЕТИ С НАРУШЕНИЯМИ СЛУХА НЕ ЛИШЕНЫ ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ПОЛУЧАТЬ ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются особенности детей с нарушениями слуха, подчеркивается важность изучения их специфических психологических потребностей, а также подчеркивается необходимость начала образовательного процесса с раннего возраста, особенно с дошкольного периода.*

Ключевые слова: *слабослышащие, инновационные технологии, язык жестов, тактильно-вибрационная чувствительность, инклюзивность, стратегии специального образования.*

Introduction: Inclusiveness is one of the most modern strategies in special education. It involves the full integration of a child with special educational needs (SEN) into school life. True inclusiveness goes beyond placing the child in a regular classroom for part or all of the day; it involves reorganizing the classroom environment and learning processes to ensure full participation of all students, including those with SEN. Ideally, an inclusive classroom should integrate several groups of children with SEN, allowing them to interact and communicate with one another. Proponents of this system believe it best prepares children for real-life situations.

Conversely, skeptics fear that teachers will be burdened with too much responsibility for children with SEN, and they may lack the necessary training and resources, potentially leading to a decline in overall education quality due to the additional attention required by children with special needs.

The Concept of Inclusive Education

Inclusive education is a developmental process aimed at adapting general education to meet the diverse needs of all children, ensuring educational accessibility for children with SEN. This approach seeks to develop teaching and learning methodologies that are flexible enough to meet various educational needs. If inclusiveness makes teaching more effective, all students, not just those with special needs, benefit.

Objectives and Tasks in Inclusive Education. Inclusive education requires the resolution of the following tasks:

- Creating necessary psychological and pedagogical conditions for the education of children and adolescents with disabilities in educational institutions.
- Implementing general education programs and correctional work focused on the capabilities of these children to promote psychological development and social adaptation.
- Guaranteeing equality in education rights for all students.
- Satisfying the needs of disabled and healthy children through active participation from society and families, fostering early adaptation to social life.
- Ensuring the right of children and adolescents with disabilities to live without being separated from their families.
- Forming a friendly and compassionate attitude in society towards children and adolescents with disabilities.

Educational Processes for Children with Hearing Impairments

The educational process for children with hearing impairments includes the following tasks:

- Creating suitable conditions for their development.
- Forming them into physically, mentally, and morally mature individuals.
- Correcting secondary impairments. This task includes four goals:
 - Developing verbal communication skills.
 - Enhancing hearing abilities.
 - Overcoming movement deficiencies.
 - Pedagogical and psychological preparation for school education and social life.

Language and Communication

For people with hearing impairments, sign language is considered their native language.

However, to ensure equal integration of preschool children and their future success, the main focus is on developing verbal communication skills. The development of speech in such children is a complex process requiring the involvement of auditory analyzers, which play a key role in speech production. Methods for developing verbal speech in children with hearing impairments must be constantly studied.

This includes the development of hearing abilities, psychological and pedagogical preparation, and vocabulary enrichment.

Innovative Methods and Technology in Education

Using educational games and didactic materials is advisable for developing verbal speech.

This helps enrich vocabulary, develop verbal communication, and utilize residual hearing capabilities. Effective collaboration between surdopedagogues and educators creates a positive developmental environment in the group, ensuring the success of the educational process.

In our country, great attention is paid to innovative technologies. In the education of children with hearing impairments, it is also necessary to introduce innovative teaching methods, develop various programs, and conduct classes using information and communication technologies (ICT).

Cluster Method

This method allows studying the main concept of a topic in the context of its interconnection with other parts. Children with hearing impairments understand relationships

between concepts and can systematize their thoughts using this method. For example, it can be used to study topics like "Mechanical Movement," "Energy," "Force," and "Friction." The key word is written down, and students divide it into branches, describing its types, differences, and giving examples. The game "Atom and Molecule" increases student activity and helps consolidate the topic. Students gain a clear understanding of the structure and movement of molecules in solids, liquids, and gases. Another advantage is that all students in the class participate. This game can also be used to study topics like "Structure of Matter," "Molecule and Its Dimensions," "Electric Charge," "Magnetic Poles."

Conclusion. Children with hearing impairments are not deprived of opportunities. An individualized approach to each student, considering their age, psychological, and physiological characteristics, allows for the effective organization of the educational process. It is important to teach in accordance with modern requirements and use innovative technologies. The main goal of the educational process is to help children with hearing impairments adapt to society and develop into well-rounded individuals.

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